

IMPROVING VIRTUAL EDUCATION THROUGH INNOVATIVE METHODS

Abduraximova Farida Komiljon qizi

Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

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Abstract: In order to provide an online course in today's student population, an educator must be imaginative and creative, as well as have a strong online presence. In today's online learning environment (also known as e-learning), keeping students thoughtfully engaged and motivated while dispensing required course content necessitates faculty facilitating a safe, nonjudgmental environment in which views, perspectives, and personal and professional experiences are encouraged. The educator must demonstrate an educator-facilitated active, student-centered learning approach in which students are held accountable for their active involvement and self-directed learning while also serving as a facilitator to further enrich the learning process. This research manifests educator's reflective practice method, which she built over many years as an early user of online education. It will investigate the organizational aspects of supporting a dynamic, robust online course.

Key words: online education, teacher, faculty development, blackboard, educator, competence.

Introduction

Facilitating an engaging online course necessitates educators developing strategies to increase student participation and foster a sense of community. This promotes collaborative learning and the development of relationships, as well as educator feedback, while allowing for independent networking and self-directed proactive learning. Furthermore, instructors must improve and support sophisticated thinking abilities while aiding students in establishing a sense of reflective self and a personal and professional ethos, which finally converts into enhanced confidence. All educational fields want students to apply what they've learned in the classroom to real-world situations.

Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate various aspects of virtual online learning, such as:

- Student perceptions of online courses (Papillion & Aaron, 2017);
- Faculty perceptions of the effectiveness of online courses (Cherry & Flora, 2017);
- Students preferred online instructor caring behaviors (Mann, 2014);

- Academic integrity in the online learning environment (Azulay Chertok, Barnes, & Gilleland, 2014; Tayaben, 2014); and (Hofmeyer et al., 2016).

Faculty development is required to improve the integration of e-learning. Students must not only be aware of the time commitment and familiar with technology, but teachers must also be trained on the pedagogical approaches necessary for an online course. Faculty members and programs that use e-learning must be aware that the educators' online presence is required to fully disseminate the course content, and that prompt and frequent feedback and faculty interactions, as well as detailed guidance to students' questions about assignments and the course process, are essential.

Participating in conversations with students and fostering peer-to-peer cooperation are crucial aspects of an engaged virtual learning dynamic. Peer-to-peer interactive design encourages cooperation and fosters a feeling of community. Attention to detail and clarity of the course, curriculum, and success criteria are required. Faculty must be organized and structured in their online content development in order for students to achieve course objectives and outcomes, and they must establish clear and defined deadlines, participation, and course expectations. Otherwise, students may regard their online learning to be inferior to that of a face-to-face classroom course.

The outputs of the instructional design process, as determined by the educator, who controls student participation and engagement while encouraging regular communication, are critical to facilitating online teaching-learning effectiveness. And, like with other learning outcomes and course assessments, measurement is based on university evaluations.

Developing online education

Designing an online community based on the university's learning platform is critical for student achievement. The educational learning platform at this author's institution is Blackboard (www.blackboard.com), however any learning platform will perform the same duties. A complete semester of information must be delivered through e-learning that encourages critical thinking, reflection, and active engagement, as well as collaborative learning that is mindfully engaged. This is a large assignment for any educator, which is why a systematic course creation approach is required. Organizing the course ahead of time reduces last-minute distractions for the educator. Setting up virtual office hours, applying the 24- to 48-hour guideline for responding to email for students and educators, and offering as much clarity and openness about course requirements and success criteria as possible are all tremendously beneficial milestones for everyone

involved. Regular communication through announcements and class emails gives further direction and keeps students on track for weekly objectives and course requirements that must be completed.

Innovative ways to enhance virtual learning

Establish an ethical learning process via well-planned virtual sessions.

It is critical that the professors create a plan for the students to follow in order for the sessions to go well. Teachers should attempt to plan ahead of time so that the speed of instruction is linked with the syllabus that must be covered within a certain period. Setting an agenda for the session, ensuring students are aware of the prerequisites, including the lessons that will be covered during the session, revision that must be completed prior to the session, assignments or tests that must be scheduled, and fixing the timing of the class so that the session runs without delay or hindrance are all part of this structured approach.

Encourage self-directed learning.

Teachers must engage students in classroom discussions and assist them in becoming self-regulated learners. Self-regulated learning guarantees that students are proactive in their learning approach, which is crucial in both offline and online classroom environments, in order for them to think positively and empower them to acquire lifetime learning abilities.

Learn how to manage internet platforms with ease.

Online teaching necessitates instructors' understanding of different components of the technological ecosystem, such as synchronous teaching, internet use, plug-in devices, and the necessary skill set to enable them accelerate their jobs. Teachers must also be familiar with technologies for administering online quizzes, examinations, and grading assignments. It is also critical for teachers to understand how technology can be integrated for various subjects based on the requirements, such as math, arts, sports, and science.

Educator's aims

Redesigning the syllabus was one of the initial learning curves. An online course syllabus needs additional information, teaching, and organization. The author discovered that repeating material in the syllabus and using online platform application announcements aided in the organization of the course for effective student results. It was critical to be exceedingly explicit on the needed assignment deadlines, down to the precise minute when an assignment would be regarded late. It is vital for both the educator and the student to be able to adjust to both foreseen and unexpected scenarios that may happen during the course. However, having clearly stated criteria and expectations is the

foundation for success. Transparency is essential in any setting to offer assistance on tasks. Learning activities are briefly mentioned in the curriculum, with additional information accessible on the learning platform.

In addition to the content required by university policy and procedures, giving detailed information on online exams, such as guidelines for completing an online exam, allows students to prepare ahead of time by checking their browser compatibility and computer abilities. This is self-evident for digitally knowledgeable students in undergraduate education classes; however, advanced degree students or nontraditional students require additional information to reduce anxiety while using an e-learning format. Tips like rebooting/restarting their computer before taking the exam have been proved to be useful in assisting pupils in closing several browser webpages.

Conclusion

The overall goal of online education is the same as it is for face-to-face didactic methodology: to inspire students to study, engage, and seek information. With online learning, new difficulties develop that necessitate the educator's creativity and innovation in fulfilling educational objectives and outcomes. Individual and group assignments may be an effective blend that helps students study independently and collaboratively. The kind of assignments is orchestrated by the course topic, with the majority of work in an e-learning course being autonomous with an infusion of teamwork. Individual work projects allow students to study at their own speed, while discussions aid to deepen knowledge of the content by sharing ideas and points of view.

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